

Effect of Saliva on Orthodontic Arch wires using Scanning Electron Microscope: An In-Vitro Study

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ABSTRACT

To determine and compare the surface morphological changes in the stainless steel, and titanium-based alloys such as TMA, and CuNiTi in saliva solution. Each sample is made up of a 60 mm long wire engaged in 6 brackets welded on 0.18×0.006 inches molar band strip and tied with ligature wire, Six such samples (Two each) from three different types of three kind of wires i.e. TMA (Titanium-Molybdenum alloy or β Titanium), SS (Stainless Steel), and CuNiTi (Copper-Nickel-Titanium) were immersed in saliva solution The sample was divided into interbracket and intrabacket area. Each sample was divided into six parts each contains interbracket and intrabacket area. The corrosion of arch wires will be detected using SEM after a period of 12 weeks of incubation in artificial saliva. The inter bracket corrosion rate was significantly less as compared to the intra bracket corrosion for all materials in saliva. There was significant increase in corrosion rate in Stainless Steel as compared to TMA and CuNiTi wires. There was significantly less corrosion was found in CuNiTi wires. There was significant increase in corrosion in saliva. The highest corrosion was seen in stainless steel followed by TMA and minimum by CuNiTi wires.

KEY WORDS: corrosion, orthodontic wires, saliva

INTRODUCTION:

Over many years, in various phases in orthodontic treatment, stainless steel, cobalt chrome and titanium-based alloys like TMA and CuNiTi have been used for correction of various clinical conditions^[1].

The orthodontic therapy involves wires and tooth bonded brackets that cause retention regions that are difficult for the patient mechanically to clean^[2].

A phenomenon called corrosion results in changes in the surface characteristics of metals. Either the loss of metal ions straight into solution or progressive dissolution of a surface film, generally an oxide or a sulphide, results in corrosion^[3].

The oral environment is an excellent climate for the corrosive assault of orthodontic equipment due to its microbiological and enzymatic phenomenon. Corrosive harm is caused to fixed orthodontic instruments which degrades physical characteristics and increases failure potential. In the light of the life

span of devices the level of such harm is of specific concern. Corrosion on sliding mechanics on sleeves and arch wire is also of major importance and may impact the anchorage^[3].

In orthodontic appliances, stainless steel, cobalt-chromium and titanium alloys are used to form a passive surface oxide film to withstand corrosion. It is prone to mechanical and chemical interruptions. This protective layer is unfailling. Although the metal surface is subjected to oxygen from air and surrounding substances, Oxide films often dissolve (passive) slowly only to reform (repassive). Acidic conditions and chloride ions can accelerate the passivation process. A diet rich in sodium chloride and acidic carbonated drinks therefore supplies corrosive agents on a frequent basis^[3,4].

Studies have screened the effect of artificial saliva of various alloys, such as stainless steel^[5], titanium^[6], nickel titanium^[7], as well as coated arch wires^[8].

The orthodontic alloys are very susceptible to different types of corrosion and manufacturers have taken measures to fight this damaging process, it includes: 1) Alloy substitution or addition; 2) Coatings Modification of the production process.

Even after using all measures the harmful effect of corrosion is not completely eliminated. The

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present study analysed and compare the corrosion of different alloys like stainless steel and titanium-based arch wires in artificial for a period of 12 weeks

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The present study was conducted in the Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopaedics, of Mansarovar Dental College and Hospital Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh. Then research got approval from Institutional Ethical Committee of college. The study was systematically scheduled to spread over a period of 3 months from June 2019 to August 2019. Single examiner performed all the examinations throughout the study. The sample size was derived in relation to the work done by Konda P et al^[1]. The final sample size comes out to be 12 samples for each group.

The study is an Analytical experimental in-vitro study. The arch wires was kept for a period of 12 weeks in an Artificial Saliva Solution and increase in corrosion due to saliva solution was compared by using Scanning Electron microscope.

The three sample of archwires made up of stainless steel, CuNiTi and TMA had been taken each with the dimension of 0.017×0.025 inch.

Simulated fixed orthodontic appliances had been constructed with band material, brackets, arch wires and ligature wires. Molar band material had been cut into strips of 60 mm each. Brackets had been welded on these band stripes equidistantly with two welds each, leaving 10 mm of space on both ends and 10 mm distance in between each bracket. Six such samples (two from each material) were prepared.

Arch wires was engaged into the bracket slots and ligated with ligature wire. After ligation, the ligature had been cut to 10 mm length from the wings of the brackets and tucked below the arch wire in unidirection. During the tests the wires had been immersed in 2 ml of artificial saliva solutions.

Group I: Comprised of simulated appliances with stainless steel arch wires

Group II: Comprised of simulated appliances with TMA arch wires

Group III: Comprised of simulated appliances with CuNiTi arch wires.

All these samples had been immersed in artificial saliva and incubated for a period of 12 weeks at 37°C in an incubator.

The Artificial saliva was taken from the “ICPA's Wet Mouth” with the principal composition — Glycerine 30 %W/V + Sodium carboxymethyl

cellulose 0.5 %W/V in a pleasantly flavoured base.

After the incubation, wire from samples of each group had been sectioned randomly into segments so that it included interbracket area and intrabacket area. This constitute a total 12 wire segments samples from each types of wires.

The samples were submitted to SEM Centre. The test was performed at CIPET Bhopal. Grid of 1mm^2 was used for overlapping the SEM pictures to evaluate and compare the amount of corrosion between stainless steel, beta-titanium and nickel-titanium archwires. The grid was overlapped on the SEM pictures and the total area showing corrosion was measured for each sample at 300X magnification.

RESULTS:

The study compared the Interbracket corrosion and Intrabacket corrosion of stainless steel, TMA (β Titanium) and Cu-Ni-Ti (Copper-nickel-Titanium) wire in artificial saliva. The comparison of interbracket surface corrosion among different materials used in study when placed for 12 weeks in artificial saliva. The maximum corrosion was found in the Stainless steel followed by TMA and minimum in the Cu-Ni-Ti wire in all the solutions and the result was statistically significant. (Table 1)

The comparison of intrabacket surface corrosion among different materials used in study when placed for 12 weeks in artificial saliva. The maximum corrosion was found in the Stainless steel followed by TMA and minimum in the Cu-Ni-Ti wire in all the solutions and the result was statistically significant. (Table 2)

The test result also shows that there is significantly more corrosion occurs in the interbracket area in comparison to the intrabacket area (Table 3).

DISCUSSION:

The oral environment is an excellent climate for the corrosive assault of orthodontic equipment due to its microbiological and enzymatic phenomenon. For some time clinicians have been concerned with corrosion of orthodontic devices in the oral setting. They focuses on two main problems: whether corrosion products, if they are manufactured, are absorbed by the body and cause either localized or systemic impacts; and the impacts of corrosion on physical characteristics of orthodontic appliances and their clinical performance.

The study tries to determine and compare the surface morphological changes in the stainless steel, and titanium-based alloys such as TMA, and CuNiTi

Table 1: Interbracket corrosion (in mm²) after 12 weeks of immersion in artificial saliva.

Types of Arch Wires	Mean	SD	f-value	p-value
Stainless Steel	902.35	8.25		
TMA	825.47	5.76	477.37	0.01(HS)
Cu-Ni-Ti	211.35	2.35		

Table 2: Intrabacket corrosion (in mm²) after 12 weeks of immersion in artificial saliva.

Types of Arch Wires	Mean	SD	f-value	p-value
Stainless Steel	137635	7.55		
TMA	141765	11.74	208.35	0.01(HS)
Cu-Ni-Ti	55539	8.25		

Table 3: Comparison of Interbracket and Intrabacket corrosion (in mm²) after 12 weeks of immersion in artificial saliva.

Type of wires	Inter Bracket	Intra Bracket	t-value	p-value
Stainless Steel	90235	137635	89.07	0.01*
TMA	82547	141765	189.47	0.01*
Cu-Ni-Ti	211.35	55539	355.05	0.01*

obtained after a period of 12 weeks of incubation in artificial saliva with the help of scanning electron microscope (SEM).

The overall result of the present study showed that the stainless steel arch wire was corroded more than the beta-titanium and nickel-titanium. Between beta-titanium (TMA) and copper-nickel-titanium, beta-titanium was more corroded than that of copper-nickel-titanium.

Shin and Hwang^[9] conducted a study in which they compared the corrosion behaviour of stainless steel and nickel-titanium and they found that stainless steel arch wires were more corrosion prone than the nickel-titanium arch wires. Similar to our study this result is consistent with most of the reports that stainless steel is more susceptible to corrosion than nickel-titanium.

In the present study the intrabacket span showed more corrosion than the interbracket span for all the arch wires which may lead to fracture of the arch wire, resulting in failure of the fixed orthodontic appliance. Movements of the arch wire in the brackets

may cause fretting corrosion, which accelerates metal loss from both the arch wire and the brackets. The corrosion resistance of the bracket, bands, tubes and arch wires relies to some extent on the presence of uniform passivated layer of chromium oxide on the metal surface. Mechanical rupturing or damage of this passivating layer will reduce the corrosion resistance property^[10].

Berradja et al evaluated the fretting wear patterns of orthodontic arch wires in dry and wet conditions and reported that stainless steel and nickel-titanium arch wires exhibited higher wear rates in the solutions than in air, indicating some synergism between the wear and corrosion processes. In the solutions the stainless steel arch wires had a much lower corrosion-wear resistance than the nickel arch wires^[11].

Muller and Chen^[12] compared the surface corrosion of stainless steel, nickel-titanium, beta-titanium and cobalt chromium, and found that beta-titanium exhibited good corrosion resistance, as did cobalt-chromium, whereas stainless steel and nickel-titanium wires showed pitting type of corrosive attack. Kim and Johnson^[13] conducted a study on corrosion of stainless steel, nickel titanium and beta-titanium orthodontic arch wires. The results showed that corrosion occurred readily in stainless steel and in some nickel-titanium wires and the breakdown potential for titanium wire could not be reached and wire remained passive throughout the entire range of 2,000 mV.

In order to improve the mechanical properties and corrosion resistance of titanium alloys and prevent the corrosion defects on the surfaces of the orthodontic appliances that influences friction, ion implanted nickel-titanium wires were introduced. With this technique, surface composition was permanently modified by inserting ionized atoms^[14]. Copper is one of the third elements that has been added to nickel-titanium, resulting in a copper-nickel-titanium alloy with many potential clinical advantages in orthodontics. Manufacturing companies claim that the addition of copper would allow the orthodontist to more easily engage larger arch wires earlier in treatment to mal-aligned teeth. This is because the copper lowers the loading stress while still providing relatively high unloading stress resulting in more effective orthodontic tooth movement of teeth^[10].

The corrosion on orthodontic reduced by Surface nitrification improves and rhodium coating. Trolic et al., (2019) found that pure artificial saliva, steel wires exhibit a larger tendency to general and

localized corrosion that NiTi wires, whose corrosion resistance is decreased by rhodium coating^[15].

The same conclusion was obtained by Kamiński J. et al. who founded that showed an increase in corrosion resistance of stainless steel after conventional glow-discharge nitriding^[16].

CONCLUSION:

The saliva present in the mouth causes surface corrosion of the orthodontic wires used for Orthodontic treatment and the surface corrosion was more in the intrabacket span as compared to the wire in interbacket span. The surface corrosion was more in the stainless steel as compared to the TMA wires and Cu-Ni-Ti wires.

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